

Variable Analysis of Work Discipline, Work Environment and Work Motivation on Employee Performance at PT. Macmahon Mining Services Martabe Project, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra, Indonesia

Haryono
Institut Teknologi dan Bisnis Asia Malang
Malang, Jawa Timur,
Indonesia

Ike Kusdyah Rachmawati
Institut Teknologi dan Bisnis
Asia Malang Malang, Jawa Timur,
Indonesia

Agus Rahman Alamsyah
Institut Teknologi dan Bisnis Asia Malang Malang, Jawa Timur,
Indonesia

Abstract:- Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity that can be achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Factors that can improve employee performance are work discipline, work environment, and work motivation. The purpose of this study was to analyze the effect of work discipline on employee performance, to analyze the influence of the work environment on employee performance, to analyze the effect of work motivation on employee performance, and to analyze work discipline, work environment, and work motivation simultaneously on employee performance. This type of research is explanatory research with a quantitative approach. This research was conducted on employees of PT. Macmahon Mining Services Martabe Project located in South Tapanuli, North Sumatra. The population in this study were all employees of PT. Macmahon Mining Services Martabe Project locations in South Tapanuli, North Sumatra totaling 673 with a sample of 87 respondents using a proportionate random sampling technique. The results showed 1) there was no significant positive influence of work discipline on employee performance, 2) there was a significant influence of work environment on employee performance, 3) there was a significant positive effect of work motivation on employee performance, and 4) there was a significant positive influence of work discipline, environment work, and motivation simultaneously on employee performance.

Keywords:- Work Discipline, Work Environment, Work Motivation, and Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

A company that aims to optimize the profit generated must be supported by quality human resources. Quality human resources, namely employees who have qualified abilities so that they are able to provide input in the form of profits to the company where the employee works [23]. The company must be able to balance the ability of employees who work in the company by having a clear vision and mission for employee welfare so that it will have an impact on employee performance [1][2].

Performance can be said as part of the work results which can be seen from the output such as quality and quantity which is the processing of employees in carrying out their duties accordance with the responsibilities given to him [3][4][5]. Good employee performance if the employee is able to achieve work standards, targets or goals, or criteria set by the company [6]. Meanwhile, bad employees will result in minimal employee productivity in the company [7]. Companies need employees who are able to work better and faster, so employees who have high performance are needed. Production in 2022 PT. Macmahon Mining Services Martabe Project South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra seen in the monthly table presented below:

Fig. 1: Production of PT Macmahon Mining Services for the Martabe Project, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra's Production

Source: HRD Division of PT Macmahon Mining, 2023

Judging from the production results of the company PT Macmahon Mining Services, the Matrabe Project, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra, in 2022 there are monthly fluctuations from January 2022 to December 2022 and work safety where there are still accidents, this shows that the employee's performance has problems that must be found. The problems faced by employees impacted PT Macmahon Mining Services, the Martabe Project, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra. These employees need attention from the company.

The company has the main role that paying attention to these employees because without the support from the company, there will be no change for the better. So companies are required to understand how to increase and improve employee performance such as increasing discipline in terms of implementing standard operating procedures SOPs in every job so that the safety management system target is achieved.

The phenomenon that occurs in the company is still found that the target achievement is still not in accordance with the time specified by the company which results in the company incurring more costs. The company will experience a decrease in profits, many employees who do not have good work discipline, such as being often late or not meeting predetermined targets, and a less conducive work environment, such as a tense or overloaded atmosphere, can reduce employee morale and motivation at work.

These problems become problems within the company to achieve company goals, so companies are looking for solutions to be able to solve problems that arise in their companies, especially regarding employee performance. Research that discusses work discipline, work environment, and motivation that has an impact on performance has already done it, including:

about how the influence of work motivation variables, work environment variables, and work discipline variables on performance in WFO companies, the results of this study indicate that there is an influence of work discipline on employee performance.. [8] concerning the effect of work discipline, work motivation, and career development on employee performance (Study at PT LKM Demak Sejahtera), the results of her research show that work discipline has no significant effect on employee performance.

The objectives to be achieved from the results of this study are: To find out and analyze the influence of discipline, work environment, work motivation on the performance of employees of PT. Macmahon Mining Services Martabe Project either partially or simultaneously.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Management is a process of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling members in the organization and what is used in other organizational resources in achieving a targeted organizational goal. [9][25]. Management can be interpreted as an activity in the use of organizational resources in achieving an organizational goal that has been designed or contained in the vision and mission of the organization. [10][11].

[12] Performance is a work of achievement that has been achieved by someone based on what has been done in the work or work in carrying out activities at the work location. Show is an act, an achievement, or a general appearance of skills. Someone will always crave appreciation for the results of his work and expect fair rewards.

According to [7], in performance measurement there are six indicators such as: 1) Quality in work or the skills and abilities of an employee in producing quality work according to standards.. 2) Work Quantity: The amount expressed in units and completed activity cycles is the amount produced which is expressed in quantity. 3) Timeliness: Completing activities on time and maximizing the time available with other activities. 4) Effectiveness: Increasing the results of each unit in the use of resources by maximizing the level of use of existing resources (labor, money, raw materials). 5) Commitment: The degree to which an employee can carry out his work functions and responsibilities to the agency or company is called commitment.

[13][14], the application of management in strengthening organizational obedience can be said to be work discipline. Besides that, discipline can be interpreted as an attitude of respecting and obeying the rules that apply orally and in writing, and being able to abstain from refusing to refuse if given a sanction if it violates the rules that have been set..

[15] components or indicators of discipline can be: 1) Attendance: see how many and how long an employee is present at the company in a certain period. 2) Compliance with regulations: employees always obey and obey the regulations that have been set, both the work system and work attendance. 3) Compliance with company work standards: an employee or all employees fully understand the existing and standardized work regulations contained in the vision, mission and objectives. 4) Vigilance at work: Employees who are alert at work will be able to minimize the level of errors at work, by being able to fully perform calculations in predicting caution will be able to overcome in minimizing errors, and by always using principles effectively and efficiently at work. 5) Work ethically: in the form of avoiding actions that disrespect or belittle customers in service and always not being involved in activities that can harm the person or the company.

[13] stated that the work environment is a condition or condition of the workplace that needs to be arranged so that it does not interfere with the work of employees and in order to gain benefits, increase productivity and reduce production costs every year.

work environment can be described with benchmarks as seen from the aspects that can shape the work environment, these parts can be described as follows [16] : 1) Service at work: Service from an employee can be used as an important aspect and must continue to be carried out by everyone in the company, 2) Working Conditions: can be interpreted where employees always try to do something good for company management so that they feel safe in work continues to be maintained, this condition at work can be seen from the existence of a good lighting system in the company, maintenance of room temperature and comfortable air, minimized noise levels, coloring in the work space, and what is important is the fulfillment of safety and health conditions in carrying out activities work. 3) Relations between employees: This relationship will be able to produce results or increase work productivity from employees. because the emergence of a good and harmonious working relationship will create and increase employee morale or the situation will be conducive to work activities, the opposite incident will be able to reduce enthusiasm and motivation in carrying out work activities as a result this can also indirectly reduce work productivity.

[17] Motivation in doing work can be interpreted as a situation or condition that influences or enhances, and at the same time directs activities at work, besides that it is also an activity in maintaining a behavior related to working conditions. then another opinion according to [17] Motivation at work is defined as the atmosphere and conditions that exist within employees or individual workers that can encourage or desire to carry out an activity that is standardized by the company..

Needs theory [6] (McClelland in his theory) deepened in David McClelland's theory with friends, where it is said that an employee's achievements as well as existing power, coupled with affiliation can be a powerful and all-powerful motivation for every employee in carrying out their duties. Furthermore, it was also conveyed that if there is a need for employees to achieve their goals, this will be related to the basic theory of character formation and will affect the results that are expected by the company. It should also be noted the importance of interpersonal work, the lifestyle of others, and the fair distribution of work. all of these things are poured into the following activities: 1) Drive for achievement: Encouragement to exceed or fair competition in achieving achievements among employees without neglecting standards. 2) The need for power: The need to be able to make another individual behave according to the rules that exist in the company without violating existing norms. 3) The need for affiliation: the need for activity in building good and harmonious relations between employees. there are some individuals who have a great desire to achieve more.

III. METHOD AND MATERIAL

This study uses a quantitative explanatory approach. Explanatory is research that explains the effect of certain variables through hypothesis testing [18]. This research approach is used to test the hypothesis and explain the influence of the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y) and the independence variables, namely work discipline (X1), work environment (X2), work motivation (X3).

The population in this study were all employees of PT. Macmahon Mining Services totaling 673 employees. Completion of the number of samples that will be used as respondents in this study is to use the Slovin method with a sample size of 87 respondents with the following distribution details:

Table 1: Calculation of Proportionate Random Sampling

Department	Number of Employees	Calculation of the proportion of respondents	The Number of Sample
HR	49	$49/673 \times 87$	6
HSEQT	33	$33/673 \times 87$	4
Commercial	6	$6/673 \times 87$	1
Mining Production	284	$28/673 \times 87$	37
Maintenance	157	$157/673 \times 87$	20
Mine Development	106	$106/673 \times 87$	14
TMF Project	38	$38/673 \times 87$	5
Total		673	87

Source: HRD Division of PT Macmahon Mining, 2023

While the detailed research indicators are described as follows:

Table 2: Research Variable and Indicator

No	Variable	Indicator
1	Work Discipline (X1)	a. Presence b. Compliance with work regulations c. Adherence to work standards d. High alert level e. Work ethically
2	Work Environment (X2)	a. Work service b. Working conditions c. Employee relations
3	Motivation (X3)	a. Achievement needs b. Need for strength c. Relationship needs
	Employee Performance (Y)	a. Work quality b. Efficiency c. Ability d. Customer satisfaction e. Team performance

Source: Various articles, processed (2023)

Based on this framework, the hypotheses in this study are:

- H1: Work discipline has a significant positive effect on employee performance
- H2: The work environment has a significant positive effect on employee performance.
- H3: Work motivation has a significant positive effect on employee performance

- H4: Work discipline, work environment, and work motivation simultaneously have a significant positive effect on employee performance.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. RESULTS

➤ *Description of Respondents*

Description of the respondents in this study consisted of age, gender, marital status of respondents, status of employees, and the results of the opinions of respondents.

Table 3: Description of Respondents

Based On Age		
Description	Frequency	Percent
> 45 years old	9	10,3
20-24 years old	11	12,6
25-30 years old	19	21,8
31-35 years old	18	20,7
36-40 years old	23	26,4
41-45 years old	7	8
Total	87	100
Based on Gender		
Male	44	50,6
Female	43	49,4
Total	87	100
Based on Marital Status		
Not Married Yet	22	25,3
Marry	65	74,7
Total	87	100
Based on Employee Status		
Permanent	84	96,6
Non-permanent	3	3,4
Total	87	100

Source: Primary data, processed (2023)

➤ *Validity and Reliability Testing*

Based on the results of the analysis all indicators in this study are valid and it can be seen that the rTable value of all statement indicators is worth 0.196 where the significance value is 5% or 0.05. Each questionnaire statement item from the results of the validity test can be declared valid.

Through the data generated in the analysis it can be understood that all variables are independent; work discipline (X1), work environment (X2), work motivation (X3), and the dependent variable employee performance (Y) have a Cronbach's Alpha value > 0.6 so that all the variables used in the following research are declared reliable.

➤ *Hypothesis testing*

Multiple linear regression analysis aims to find out together two or more independent variables on a dependent variable. The independent variables in this study include work discipline (X1), work environment (X2), work motivation (X3), and employee performance (Y). The results of the analysis of multiple linear regression tests in this study with the help of computerization (SPSS) are presented in the table below:

Table 4: SPSS Analysis Results of Multiple Linear Regression

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	,168	,421		,399	,691
	Work Discipline (X1)	,091	,091	,060	,996	,322
	Work Environment (X2)	,266	,081	,270	3,290	,001
	Motivation (X3)	,590	,080	,619	7,373	,000
a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (Y)						

Source: Primary data, processed (2023)

Table 4 shows that the results of the t-test for the variables in this study are as follows: 1) Work discipline has an insignificant value of 0.322 > 0.05 with a t-count value of 0.996. These results indicate that the value is not significant on the work discipline variable > 0.05. Then the first hypothesis is rejected and work discipline has no significant effect on employee performance. 2) The work environment has a significant value of 0.001 < 0.05 with a t-count of 3.290. These results indicate that the significant value of the work environment variable is < 0.05. Then the second hypothesis is accepted and the work environment has a significant influence on employee performance. 3) Work motivation has a significant value of 0.000 < 0.05 with a t-count of 3.976. These results indicate that the significant value of the work motivation variable is < 0.05. Then the hypothesis is accepted and has a significant influence on employee performance. From these results, it can be said that hypothesis 1 in this study is stated to be unproven while hypotheses 2 and 3 are stated to be statistically proven.

The 4th hypothesis is tested by simultaneous testing (F test). The F test results from the processed SPSS results in this discussion show a significant value of 0.000. means that the significance value < 0.05. so it is conveyed that the 4th hypothesis can be accepted statistically, or it can be interpreted that the variables of work discipline, work environment, and work motivation together have an influence on the performance of employees. So that the 4th hypothesis is declared statistically proven.

B. DISCUSSION

A. Effect of Work Discipline (X1) on Employee Performance (Y)

From the results of the t-test in table 17 it is known that partially the value of t-hit > t-table or 0.996 > 1.985 so that the results can be drawn that work discipline partially does not affect employee performance. This description is proven by the results of this study that the work discipline variable has a significant value of 0.001 < 0.05, meaning that work discipline has no significant effect on employee performance.

Work discipline is an attitude or behavior that intends to comply with all organizational regulations based on self-awareness to comply with organizational regulations.[9]. Work discipline aims to make a person able to distinguish what things should be done, what must be done, what can be done, and what should not be done (because these are things that are prohibited). If employee work discipline is high, it will affect the performance of employees in carrying out their duties and work effectively and efficiently and have an impact on the results of achieving company goals.

Based on the descriptive results of work discipline owned by employees of PT. Macmahon Mining Services Martabe Project South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra is classified as very low, so the management is more creative in creating a model for improving employee work discipline by providing rewards for employees who have not been absent for 1 year, work according to agreed organizational procedures and provide contribution to the company. The reward is of course adjusted to the needs of employees. If the management understands what the employee needs, the employee will certainly have high work discipline, but conversely if management cannot understand what the employee needs, of course, the employee's work discipline will be low and have an impact on employee performance.

B. Effect of Work Environment (X2) on Employee Performance (Y)

The results of this study indicate that the work environment has a significant value of $0.001 > 0.05$ with a t-count value of 3.290, while the t-table value is 1.985 meaning that the work environment has an influence on employee performance. The work environment of each company is certainly different because companies that have different production work environments are created according to their work production [24]. Like PT. Macmahon Mining Services Proyek Martabe South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra is a gold mining company. A gold mining production company is seen as a type of company service, its employees carry out more of their work activities outside the company. While the company itself has equipped uniforms for employee safety.

The work environment can exist when an employee is carrying out work activities or a condition where employees do work either individually or in groups [19][8][20]. A good work environment can spur high employee performance. This description contradicts the results of this study.

Based on the descriptive results of the work environment at PT. Macmahon Mining Services Proyek Martabe, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra is classified as low. This does not affect the performance of employees of PT. Macmahon Mining Services for the Proyek Martabe, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra, it has been proven that many employees have permanent status. Another reason is that the work environment does not affect the performance of employees at PT. Macmahon Mining Services Proyek Martabe South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra, because there is a sense of responsibility to the family as evidenced by many employees who are married. If employees of PT. Macmahon Mining Services Proyek Martabe South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra works as a family responsibility, of course, the work environment will not affect the employee's performance.

C. Effect of Work Motivation (X3) on Employee Performance (Y)

The results of this study indicate that work motivation has a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$ with a t-count value of 7.373, with a t-table value of 1.985 meaning that it can be interpreted that work motivation has a significant influence on employee performance. If employee motivation is high, employee performance also increases, but conversely, if employee motivation is low, employee performance is also low/bad.

Based on the descriptive results, the work motivation of PT. Macmahon Mining Services for the Proyek Martabe, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra is still relatively low. This is the management of PT. Macmahon Mining Services Proyek Martabe, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra needs to provide support to increase the motivation of its employees. If seen from the descriptive results, the average employee is married, of course, the employee needs living expenses for a larger family. The management of PT. Macmahon Mining Services Proyek Martabe Project South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra understands that all employees of PT. Macmahon Mining Services Proyek Martabe South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra by increasing motivation through meeting activities by having lunch together/holiday together by providing time for sharing between management and employees regarding what employees complain about in doing work can be done in one year once to find out the development of the company whether there is a decrease or increase. If the motivation from the management of PT. Macmahon Mining Services Proyek Martabe, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra, in accordance with the employees, of course, these employees will have high work motivation and have an impact on PT. Macmahon Mining Services Martabe Project, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra.

D. The Effect of Work Discipline (X1), Work Environment (X2), Work Motivation (X3) Simultaneously on Employee Performance (Y)

The results of this study that the results of the F test have a significant value of 0.000. this shows that the variables of work discipline, work environment, and work motivation simultaneously have a significant influence on employee performance. These three variables are very important in shaping employee performance. Descriptive results regarding the performance of PT. Macmahon Mining Services for the Proyek Martabe, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra is still relatively low. Based on observations from the descriptive respondents that the employees of PT. Macmahon Mining Services Proyek Martabe, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra, requires motivation from management. The motivation is adjusted to the needs of its employees. The results of the analysis of motivational variables that most influence the performance of employees of PT. Macmahon Mining Services Proyek Martabe, South Tapanuli Regency, North Sumatra. Work motivation is the first gate, work motivation itself can be in the form of a comfortable work environment and a decent salary for employees. If employee motivation is high, of course, work discipline is also high.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, the conclusions to be conveyed in this study are as follows: 1) Work Discipline (X1) has no effect on Employee Performance (Y), so hypothesis 1 which states work discipline has an effect on employee performance is rejected or not accepted. 2) Work Environment (X2) affects Employee Performance (Y), so hypothesis 2 which states the work environment influences employee performance is proven or accepted. 3) Motivation (X3) affects employee performance (Y), so hypothesis 3 which states motivation influences employee performance is proven or accepted. 4) Work Discipline (X1), Work Environment (X2), and Motivation (X3) jointly affect Employee Performance (Y), so that hypothesis 4 states Work Discipline (X1), Work Environment (X2), and Motivation (X3) jointly affect Employee Performance (Y) is proven or accepted.

The results of the study show that work discipline, work environment, and motivation have a joint effect on employee performance which can be used as material for consideration for management in making policies to improve employee performance. Work discipline in completing tasks with full responsibility and complying with the regulations set by the company greatly influences employee performance [21] [6][22]. In addition, improving employee performance can also be done by paying attention to employee motivation. In spurring an increase in employee morale, companies really need to look at the needs of employees as well as other factors that can influence improving their work system, so employees really need to be continuously motivated with the aim of continuing to improve work results or company progress.

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